

doi:10.5281/zenodo.16414342

Misery Index And Global Financial Crisis On A Developing Economy

¹Michael Mpia Ph.D & ²Ozuru, Eucharia C.

¹School of Financial Studies

Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Rumuola, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

E-mail:ngeimike@yahoo.com/ Tel: 08037047693

³School of General Studies (GNS)

Captain Elechi Amadi Polytechnic, Rumuola, Port Harcourt, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study examines the effect of misery index and global financial crises on a developing economy like Nigeria. The study adopted unemployment and inflation rates as proxy for misery index and global financial crises while external reserves was considered for a developing economy (Nigeria). In the cause of the study, it was discovered that banks in developed nations were basically responsible for such economic upheavals as a result of over speculative tendencies of bank officers. Therefore, it is imperative that banks officers should be allowed to go on quarterly training with the aim of being abreast with current development in the financial sector globally.

Keywords: Crises, Economic activities, Economic policy, losses, inflation, unemployment, investors.

INTRODUCTION

Financial crisis is considered as a sudden down turn in the value of financial institutions and the economy at large, such situation can be triggered by several factors such as negative sentiments, fear and panic. In the views of Adrian, Tobins and Shin (2009) they opined that this is a moment where financial networks and markets suddenly become markedly unable or strained to the point where there is the likelihood of collapse. While De Nicolo, Giovanni and Marquez (2006) asserted that such crises affects the entire economy. Therefore global financial crises is viewed as a worldwide economic down turn. This period is also considered as a period of general decline or depression in economic activity which have resulted in mass unemployment, general fall in profits, wages, interest rates, consumption, expenditure, investments and factories closure and construction of all types of capital goods.

At various times, Global financial crises is always traceable to crisis in one of the developed countries economic policy or conflict. Furthermore, several global financial crises are linked with banking panics, stock market crisis, and currency crisis among others Borio, C. and Mcquirel (2011). In Nigeria, the country also had her own share of these crises as a result of losses sustained by investors in the capital market, coupled with sudden price source of essential materials which has affected the manufacturing sector of the economy.

Misery index which is also referred to as economic discomfort index is applied at developing a comprehensive index which takes cognizance of several indicators that could be used in tracking macro-economic conditions along business cycles. Misery index is also used to measure the degree of economic distress that is felt as a result of risk of joblessness with associated increase in the cost of living. Misery index has two major components, which are inflation and unemployment rates (Federal Reserve Banks,

2020). Misery index is considered as the sum of unemployment and inflation rates, and as such it is used to appraise the financial well-being of a given population. But in the views of Wu (2013) he asserted that higher inflation rate coupled with worsening unemployment rate are viewed to create economic and social cost for any given nation. While Yilmaz (2018) opined that a low misery index value indicates a better economic performance while a higher index value reflects a poor economic performance and as such the higher the index value the greater the misery is felt by the citizens. In this study therefore, the objective of this study is to determine the effect of misery index on global financial crises with special reference to Nigeria. This is because their continuation affects a nation's economy which can also be used to determine the overall economic health of a nation. Fiscal crisis refers to problems identified in government balance sheet. It can also occur during recession and period of high unemployment thus it is also possible for government financial crisis to bring about financial crisis directly or indirectly. The study adopted unemployment and inflation rates as proxy for modern index and external reserve as proxy for global financial crises.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Misery index measures the degree of economic distress, such distress could be attributed to risk of joblessness combined with an increase in the cost of living. It is also viewed as a measure of economic distress due to its significant financial burden it imposes on the citizens. In the views of Nasko (2016) he posited that such index also includes banks lending rates. While Von (1990) was of the view that increases in long term interest rates and economic growth below what he termed the average could also lead to misery. He further argued that misery increases inflation rate where unemployment rate will also go up.

Misery Index is also viewed as an economic indicator that considers unemployment rate and inflation rate to determine economic performance. And as such a higher misery indicates higher degree of economic rigidities. It also, considers economic hardship faced by citizens as a result of high level of unemployment rate and surge in prices as in the case of Nigeria. Therefore, it is an important measure for assessing an economy (office for national statistics, 2022). But in considering this position, Shostak (2023) retrieved asserted that Misery Index as a simplified measure does not in Moses cases capture all aspects of the economy. And as such other economist analysts were of the opinion that certain modifications should be introduced such as other economic factors.

Global financial crises are considered to be more severe because it leads to recession, higher unemployment and as such it requires serious government intervention. In the views of Borenstein (2024) he asserted that these crises could lead to contagion economic down turns and government intervention leading to long term effect on the economy.

In the views of Kelly (2008), He opined that the index measures the level of inflation which constitutes two important indicators of macro index. This is because the higher the index, the greater the misery is felt by the citizens. (Inylaina, 2013). He further modified the misery index by the sum of unemployment, inflation and bank lending rates less the percentage change in the real GDP per capita but where you intend to achieve an ideal level of economic efficiency, employers will need to find workers and as such a healthy economy requires some level of inflation.

Global financial crises refers to a period of extreme stress in global financial markets and banking system (Epstein 2020). It affects the rest of the world through linkages in the global financial system. Many financial institutions around the world incurred huge losses and relied on their governments for support so as to avoid bankruptcy. Furthermore, many workers are bound to lose their jobs. Thus, misery index has been considered as a popular method of gauging the true position of an economy.

- i. Global financial crises unfolded as a result of high level of borrowers were unable to comply with the obligation of repaying their loans.
- ii. Stress in the financial system
- iii. Spill over of these problems to other economies

- iv. Financial market panics
- v. Low response in policies towards global growth
- vi. Lowering of interest rates by central banks
- vii. Increase in government spending

International investment banks were also disconnected from the entire global financial system due to various forms of compromise. It is also important to note that the banking system is a continuation of the financial institutions which also viewed for being responsible for safe keeping and lending of money (CBN, 2016) Thus financial stability index is considered to be important as a result of its capabilities because it considers a nation's financial structure, financial innovations and also allows policy makers to monitor and review all stressful situations as it affects the banks or personal levels.

CAUSES OF GLOBAL FINANCIAL CRISIS

The causes are listed as follows

- Excessive risk taking in a favourable macroeconomic environment.
- Increased borrowing by banks and investors
- Regulations and policy errors

In the views of World Bank (2012) they asserted that global financial crises had underscored the disastrous consequences of weak financial sector policies. They further stated that financial crises has exposed potential disastrous consequences for financial developments and their impact on economic outcomes.

These crises have challenged conventional thinking in financial sector policies (Wu, 2013), This position is further upheld by world bank (2021) where they asserted that the crisis has challenged conventional thinking in financial sector policies on how best to achieve sustainable development. In responding to these crises, the financial authorities where compelled to strengthen their regularities and oversight functions on banks and other financial institutions. Such regulations must consider how to spread risks throughout the financial system and how such can be prevented. Furthermore, banks are to operate with lower leverage, all these where put in place with the aim of restoring confidence in the financial system and to further contain the magnitude of the crises on the economy. In this study therefore unemployment rate and inflation rate are considered as proxy for misery index while external reserves was considered as proxy for global financial crises.

Inflation rate is considered because the indicator measures the change in prices of consumer goods and service acquired, used and paid by household. Thus, rate of inflation is one of the indicators monitored by monetary authorities in certain monetary policy.

Inflation is concerned with sustained increase in the general price level of goods and services in any given economy over a given period of time. The effect of rise in prices leads to a situation where each unit of a currency will buy few goods and services. Thus, inflation reflects a total reduction in the purchasing power attached to per unit of money. And as such there is this general assumption that high rate of inflation is due to excess growth in money supply (Onoh, 2017). He further stated that long sustained period of inflation is as a result of money supply growing faster than the rate of economic growth one can therefore say that inflation is related to money supply. Thus the term inflation refers to increase in the amount of money in circulation. (Amin and Anono, 2012). But in the views of Olu and Idin (2015) he opined that the effect of money on inflation is more pronounced when government financial spending in times of crises such as civil war as a result of printing more money will definitely lead to hyper inflation which is a situation where prices double excessively. From the foregoing, it has been observed that inflation remains a serious macroeconomic change to developing nations (Anyanwu, 2017). Despite several government policies and programmes, the economic has witness and experience high inflation coupled with attendant consequences on the most vulnerable in Nigeria. Since the government has

continued to operate deficit budget over the years, it has also contributed high inflation rate Hank and Steve, (2024).

Although some level of inflation is considered to be appropriate in an economy (Mpia,2020), thus, inflation measures are basically modified either through weight of goods in a specified basket or various methods of comparison that are considered over a period of time leading to a situation where inflation numbers are mostly seasonally adjusted with the aim of differentiating expected cyclical cost shifts so when considering inflation, monetary authorities can focus on prices of certain kinds or other special indices. Since inflation can be anticipated over a period of time in the near future, the two basic approaches to evaluate such analysis are also adopted which are adaptive expectation and rational expectation both affects the economy of a given nation in several dimensions (Inyiama, 2013). But inflation driving periods of high inflation, the value of the domestic currency will always reduce which will affect the economy negatively (Folorunso and Abiola, 2000).

As a result of the above, consumers are faced with the problem of high prices as a result of higher production cost (Udoh and Isaiah, 2018). Although inflation is considered as purely a money phenomenon. It has unprecedented affects on any economy because it distorts price mechanism and also discourages investment and savings (Hossian et al 2012).can be controlled where money supply matches economic growth at a given period of time. Although rapid and prolonged inflation can become chronic which will also affect savings, it can also encourage capital flights. Unemployment rate is the most widely used indicator of the well- being of a labour market and an important measure of the State of an economy (Ilo, 1998). According to Ilo guidelines, a person is unemployed if the person is A not working, B currently available for work and seeking work.

Unemployment have generated several debates due to its negative affect on the society and the economy at large. In Nigeria, there is high level of unemployment which has affected the economy negatively. Such negative disposition of unemployment has led to high level of crime, prostitution and several other vices. This has made the government to review its policy thrust coupled with various assistance from international agencies with the aim of bring this under control but to a larger extent its impact has been very alarming (Mpia, 2022). While Onoh, (2012) asserted that unemployment makes workers to suffer financial losses and hardship which further affects their families. It also affects economy through spending. While (Jhingan, 2004) opined that unemployment has become one of the major issues facing countries. But Gbosi, (2011) stated that one key macroeconomic goals is the achievement of full employment and where this is not utilizing its available resources. But in Nigeria, the government has applied several policy measures yet it has been difficult to cures unemployment. Thus, unemployment constitutes serious developmental problem. This is because it increases the rate of crime thus, a social problem, thereby it is viewed as creating dangerous signal to al facets of the economy Herbert, (2006). Towards this background, Economic watch (2005) asserted that unemployment in Nigeria is viewed as one of the most critical problems confronting the country. Unemployment also has social consequences as it influences the rate of crime.

Furthermore, the proportion of workers unemployed also indicates how well a country's human resources are used and serves as index of economic movement which could be positive or negative Afdebi, (1999). Therefore, unemployment constitutes a series of serious developmental problems and is increasingly becoming more serious in developing countries.

External Reserve is also referred to international Reserve (Bianch, Juan and Martinez (2013) While IMF (2007) posited that international reserves consists of official public sector foreign assets which are considered to be available and controlled by the monetary authorities for financing of payment imbalances. Through various interventions in the exchange markets with the aim of affecting currency exchange rate and or for other purposes. But it is imperative to mention that countries hold external reserves in foreign currencies with the aim of maintaining a desirable exchange rate policy through monitoring and controlling the foreign exchange market (Rodrick, 2006). Basically, external reserves are

needed so as to guard against financial crises (Mendoza, 2004). Thus, external reserves has aided countries secure international credit worthiness which also facilitates various forms of financial assistance in the form of debts amongst others. Aizenman and Marion (2004) pointed out that the size of international transactions, their volatility exchange rate arrangement and political stability are the some of the key determinant of international reserves holding in most countries. Towards this backdrop several reasons could be adduced for holding external reserved in the views of Burka and lane (2001) they asserted that financial depth and external indebtedness also influences international reserves. But Ibrahim, (2011) was of the opinion that external reserve holding is expected to increase with economic size and the volume of international transactions. Holding of external reserve is one of the ways to protect an economy from the effect of external shocks and maintaining macro economy stability Nzotta, (2004) opined that foreign reserves are generated when exchange rate disbursements are lower then foreign exchange receipts, the surplus thus gives rise to foreign reserves and as it is seen as foreign exchange surplus of a country that has been accumulated over time. Based on this its effect on unemployment and inflation rates cannot be treated with levity. But the central bank of Nigeria holds external reserves for reasons listed below.

- i. External reserves serve as a form of support or backing.
- ii. International trade settlements can be financed by reserves especially when there is deficit between exports proceeds and import.
- iii. External reserves can also be used as form means of holding Sovereign Wealth Fund (SWF).
- iv. The Central bank of Nigeria uses reserves to deal with exchange rate volatility.
- v. External reserves are accumulation has to shore up the country's credit ratings and credit worthiness because credit Agencies consider the holding of reserves in their rating of a country.
- vi. Holding of reserves serves as a form shock absorber in times of global financial crisis.
- Vii. External reserve are accumulated for emergencies and natural disasters. Therefore, external reserve holding is considered as an economic insurance against financial crisis.

METHODS

Model Specification

This study made use of secondary data obtained from CBN's statistical bulletin. The data covered a period of 41 years (1981-2022). Based on these, a model was developed to determine the effect of misery index on global financial crises in Nigeria. As a result of the above, econometrics method of data analysis was applied with the model stated below.

ETR = FCMF, (UNE)

This is transformed with the aid of logarithm which is stated as follows:

$$\log \text{ Etr} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log \text{ INF} + \beta_2 \log \text{ ume} + \text{eit}$$

where

ETR = External reserve

INF = Inflation rate

UNrm = Unemployment rate

Eit = error term

β_0 = Intercept

β_1 = estimated parameters

DATA ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1

From Figure 1, the three macroeconomic variables appear to be stationary over time.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics for EXTR, INFL, and UNEMPL

Statistics	EXTR	INFL	UNEMPL
Mean	19998.52	19.15	10.71
Maximum	58472.88	72.84	35.00
Minimum	36.61	5.39	1.80
Std Dev.	17578.43	1722	9.05
Skewness	0.46	1.79	1.13
Kurtosis	1.69	4.95	3.43
Jarque- Bera	4.04	26.32	8.44
Probability	0.1324	0.0000	0.0147

Table I above shows the descriptive statistics for external reserve, inflation, and unemployment, while Figure I shows the time series plot for the variables under consideration. From Table 1, external reserve averaged N19,998.52 billion over the sampled period, while average values of inflation and unemployment rates are 19.15% and 10.71% respectively. Also, the skewness indicates that the three study variables have a positively skewed distribution. On the other hand, the kurtosis coefficient indicates that external reserve has a platykurtic distribution, while both inflation and unemployment rates have a leptokurtic distribution. All these indicate that none of the variables may have a normally distributed series. However, the JR statistic fails to reject the normal distribution hypothesis for external reserve, while it clearly rejects the normality hypothesis for both inflation and exchange rate.

Figure 1: Timer Series Plot for LEXTR, LINFL and LUNEMPL

Empirical Analysis

Table 2: ARDL Results for LEXTR, LINFL, and LUNEMPL

Variable	Coefficient	P-value
Model Estimates		
LEXTR(-1)	0.6983	0.0000
LINFL	-0.3633	0.1295
LUNEMPL	0.7565	0.2333
LUNEMPL(-1)	-0.7471	0.3062
Constant	3.7110	0.0117
CointEq(-1)	-0.3016	0.0352
Diagnostic Statistics		
R-Squared	0.4900	
Adjusted R-s		

Table 2 above reports the ARDL results for the dynamic relationship between LEXTR, LINFL and LUNEMPL. The model estimation is based on White's residuals; hence our results are not affected by any misspecification bias due to heteroskedasticity. The model order determination is based on the Schwarz information criterion (SIC), which prefers a model that minimizes its value. As shown in Figure 2, the SIC prefers an ARDL (1,0,1) and hence suggests that a model with 1 lag of external reserve as 1 lag of unemployment as additional explanatory variables is the most plausible specification for the dynamic relationship between external reserve, inflation and unemployment. This shows that external reserve is persistent, and is a function of its external reserve, while the impact of unemployment extends over the next period.

Schwarz Criteria (top 20 models)

Figure 2: Model Order Selection

Table 2: ARDL Results for LEXTR, LINFL, and LUNEMPL

Variable	Coefficient	P-value
Model Estimates		
LEXTR(-1)	0.6983	0.0000
LINFL	-0.3633	0.1295
LUNEMPL	0.7565	0.2333
LUNEMPL(-1)	-0.7471	0.3062
Constant	3.7110	0.0117
CointEq(-1)	-0.3016	0.0352
Diagnostic Statistics		
R-squared	0.4900	
Adjusted R-squared	0.4263	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0001	
Durbin-Watson stat	1.3713	
BG (LM) statistic	0.5685	0.7526

From Table 2, the LEXTR(-1) is positive, sizable, and highly statistically significant. The coefficient of 0.6983 shows that a percentage increase in the current external reserve would, on average, lead to about 0.70% increase in external reserve in the next period. This clearly shows that the Nigerian external reserve is highly predictable on the basis of its previous performance. Also, the speed of adjustment coefficient (CointEq (-1)) is negative and highly significant, indicating that the estimated ARDL model is stable and has long-run implication. The coefficient of -0.3016 shows that external reserve would adjust back to its equilibrium level after suffering a shock, and about 30% of this adjustment would occur in the next period.

The coefficient on LINFL is negative but not statistically significant. The estimated coefficient of -0.3633 shows that a percentage increase in the current inflation level would, on average, cause external reserve to concurrently decrease by about 0.36%, which is sizable and appears to be significant in economic sense. Hence, rising inflation is associated with decreased external reserve. Unemployment rate has a dynamic or spread effect on external reserve. However, while the coefficients on LUNEMPL and LUNEMPL (-1) both are sizable, they are individually not statistically significant. The coefficients of 0.7565 and -0.7471 show that if the current unemployment rate increases by 1%, external reserve would concurrently increase by approximately 0.76%, but would also decrease by about 0.75% one period after such that the net effect is 0.01%, which is marginal. Hence, there is evidence that both inflation and unemployment have no statistically significant effect on external reserve.

From Panel B, although, the Durbin Watson statistic is less than the expected 2, it is much greater than the R-squared, suggesting that our empirical results are not spurious. The Adjusted R-squared of 0.4263 indicates that about 43% of the model variance are explained by the included regressors, while the F-statistic indicates that the fitted model is highly statistically significant. The 130 (LM) statistic is not statistically significant, implying that the fitted ARDL model is not plagued by serial correlation, an indication that the empirical results are not affected by specification biases.

CONCLUSION

From the results obtained in the cause of this study, it was evidenced that global financial crises led to global economic down turn which affected several financial and economic institutions globally which also affected the price of goods and services and generally default by debtors. Such crises arose from bank panics and other economic indices that affected the world economy. Towards this end, there is need for policy makers and operators of various financial institutions that their actions affects the world at large and as such they should be advised on certain actions they might undertake and its impact on the world economy. Secondly, bank officials and CEOs should be very prudent in their speculative tendencies.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Since these crises emanated from various forms of device by financial institutions mostly in developed countries, there is the need for caution and adherence to banking regulations in the banking sector as a result panics. There is also the need therefore, for the monetary authorities to put in place further checks on the banking institutions with aim of avoiding such occurrence of down turns in the financial sectors of the economy. There should be quarterly training and lectures on managers and CEOs of various financial institutions with the aim of addressing such issues as it relates to fear, panic and negative sentiments in the near future.

REFERENCES

- Adrian, T. and Hyun, S.S. (2009) Money, liquidity and Monetary Policy. *American Economic Review* Vol. 99. NO. 2.
- Aminu, U and Anono, A. Z (2012) Effect if inflation on the growths and development of the Nigerian economy. (An empirical Analysis) *International Journal of Business and social sciences*.
- Anyanwu, J.C. (2017) *Monetary economics: Theory, policy and institutions* Onitsha Hybrid publishers
- Borio, and Mcguie, R. (2011) *Global Credit and Domestic Credit Booms* BIS Quarterly Review. Di
- Nicolo, Gianni, Marquezi R. (2006) *Lending Booms and Lending Standards*, *Journals of finance* Vol. 61, NO.5.
- Inyiama, O.I. (2013) Does inflation weaken economic growth? Evidence from Nigeria: *European journal of accounting Auditing and fiancé research*, vol. 1
- Olu, J.F. and Idih, E.O (2015) *Inflation and economic growth in Nigeria*. *Journal of Economics and international business mgt.* vol. 3(1).
- World Bank, (2012) *The level of indebtedness and the performance of sub-sahara African States: A dynamic study*.